

PREPARATION FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY BY DEVELOPING INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY OF FUTURE TEACHERS

Fergana State University

Teacher of the department of social and humanitarian sciences

Y.H. Kipchakova

Abstract

At the modern stage of the development of our society, there is an increasing need for creative individuals capable of developing and improvising unconventional solutions in problematic situations. This is happening as a result of rapid growth of information flow, development of science and technology, fundamental changes in politics, economy, moral standards of the country.

Key words

Improvisation, competence, innovation, creativity, independent education, educational paradigm, educational standard, integration, differentiation, hierarchical model.

Bugungi kunda axborot oqimining shiddatli o`shishi(jamiyatda axborot turlarining keskin o`shishi) sababli har bir yangi avlod asosiy bilimlarni talab etuvchi butunlay yangi vaziyatga duch kelmoqda. Zamonaviy ta`lim muassasalari ijtimoiy faol ijodiy tafakkurga ega shaxsni, bitiruvchilarda innovatsion faolligini rivojlantirish orqali kasbiy tayyorgarligini takomillashtirishga yo`naltirilgan malakalarni shakllantirishga, yangi texnologiyalarni o`zlashtirish, mustaqil ta`lim, mavjud bilimlarni chuqurlashtirish va kengaytirishni o`z oldiga qo`ygan. Yetakchi olimlar (N. Sh. Ruziqulova, I. A. Eshmamatova, U. Sh. Begimqulov, N. A. Muslimov, V. V. Serikov, I. S. Yakimanskaya, E. V. Bondarevskaya va boshqalar)bilim-ma`rifatli

ta'lim paradigmasiga asoslangan mavjud an'anaviy maktab modeli bugungi zamon talabiga javob bermasligini takidlamodalar.

Mamlakatimiz ta'lim tizimini takomillashtirish, ayniqsa dolzarbdir. Keyingi davrda ilmiy davralarda ta'limga bilimli va kompetentli yondashuv mavzusi faol muhokama qilinmoqda, bo'lajak o'qituvchi amaliyotda umumiy o'rta ta'limda mehnat faoliyatini boshlashi uchun mutaxassis bo'lib shakllanishi e'tiborga olinmoqda. Umumiy o'rta ta'lim mazmunini takomillashtirishning xukumat strategiyasida umumiy o'rta ta'lim muassasalari faoliyatining asosiy natijalari o'z-o'zidan bilim va malakalar tizimi bo'lishi shartligi aniq belgilab berilgan, intellektual huquqiy-fuqarolik, kommunikatsion, axborot va boshqa sohalar asosiy kompetentlik jamlanmasi shakllanishi zarur.

Bu ta'limda an'anaviy yondashuv bilan aloqador inson qobiliyati bilan o'quv syujetlari, hamda ta'limiy vaziyatlari doirasida samarali harakat qilishga qodirligi bilan bog'liq. Komponentli yondashuv birinchi o'ringa ta'lim oluvchining axborotlarni egallashini emas, balki hayotda yuzaga keladigan muammolarni hal etish malakasini qo'yadi.

Adabiyoylar tahlili ko'rsatishicha „komponentlik“ atamasi umumiy o'rta ta'lim standarti loyihasiga kiritilgan bo'lsa-da, ilmiy-ta'limiy hamjamiyat uning ta'rifi bo'yicha yagona fikr ishlab chiqmagan. Barcha ta'riflar uchun umumiy tushuncha shaxsning turli vazifalarni bajarishga qodirligini anglatadi.

Pedagogik doiralarda kompetentli yondashuv muammosining muhokamasi davrida ko'pincha pozitsiya so'zi tilga olinadi, an'anaviy ta'limda, „kompetentlilik tushunchasi hech qanday yangicha tamoyilli yondashuvni qo'shmaydi“, kompetentlilik maktablarda allaqachon ishlatiladigan tushunchaning yangi talqinidir[80;66-b]

Innovatsion faolligini rivojlantirish masalalarining tarixiy ildizlari sharq mutafakkirlari Abu Rayhon Beruniy, Abu Ali ibn Sino, Abu Nasr Farobiy, Abdulla Avloniy asarlarida aks etgan. Tarixiy meroslarimizda kompetentsiyaviy bilim olishga yo'naltirilganlik g'oyalarining jamiyat taraqqiyotidagi ahamiyati va

muhimligi masalalari haqida ko`plab fikr-mulohazalar bayon etilgan.

O. A. Abdullina, E. M. Borisova, E. F. Zeer, L. S. Vigotskiy, A. N. Leont`ev, M. I. Lukyanova, A. K. Markova, S. L. Rubinshteyn va boshqalar oz ilmiy ishlarida bolajak kasb ta`imi o`qituvchilarida axborot kompetentligini shakllantirish, ularni axborot bilan ishlash ko`nikmalarini o`zlashtirish, faoliyatiga tayyorlashning psixologik –pedagogik asoslari haqida e`tiborga molik fikrlarni ilgari surishgan bo`lishsa, O. Abduquddusov, R. X. Djuraev, U. I. Inoyatova, Z. K. Ismoilova, N. A. Muslimov, N. Nishonaliyev, Q. T. Olimov, X. F. Rashidov, O. Tolipov, A. R. Xodjaboyev, D. O. Ximmataliyev, Sh. S. Sharipov va boshqalar ilmiy-tadqiqotlari bo`lajak o`qituvchilarda axborot olish haqidagi bilim, ko`nikma va malakalarni shakillantirish, malakali kadrlar tayyorlash masalasini ilmiy-uslubiy jihatdan tahlil etish.

Shuningdek, A. R. Xodjabaevning ilmiy ishlarida mehnat va kasb talimi o`qituvchisi o`quv-metodik ta`minotning pedadogik asoslari ishlab chiqilgan va ularni amaliyotda qo`llash yo`llari ko`rsatib berilgan. Bo`lajak o`qituvchi shaxsini shakillantirish va tayyorlash jarayonini ta`minlovchi qator omillar majmuasi va shart-sharoitlari aniqlangan, hamda asoslangan, o`quv-tarbiya jarayoni tizim sifatida tavsiflangan[168;314-b]

Kasb-hunar ta`limi va mehnat ta`limi o`qituvchilarini tayyorlashning nazariy va uslubiy jihatlari R. H. Jo`rayevning fundamental tadqiqotlarida ham o`z aksini topgan. [84]. Yoshlarni mehnat ta`limiga tayyorlashni tadqiq etish jarayonida egallangan bilimlarni nazariy va shu bilan birgalikda metodik jihatdan takomillashtirishni talab qiladi.

Horijiy tadqiqotlarda mamlakatimizda axborot kompetentligi rivojlanishini har jihatdan asoslash va o`rganish, bizning fikrimizcha, pedagog shaxsining rivojiga o`z ta`sirini ko`rsatishi ta`kidlangan.

U. I. Inoyatov kasb-hunar ta`limi muassasalarida ta`lim sifatini nazorat qilish va boshqarishning nazariy va boshqarishning nazariy va tashkiliy-metodik asoslarini ilmiy asoslagan. [98]Boshqaruv va nazorat har bir sohada raqobat

muhitini vujudga keltirib, rivojlanish, yuqori sifat va samaradorlik omili bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Q. T. Olimovning fundamental tadqiqotida o'quv adabiyotlarini yaratishning nazariy va amaliy jihatlarini o'rganilgan, o'quv- uslubiy adabiyotlarning yangi avlodini yaratish konsepsiyasi ilmiy asoslanib, o'quv jarayoni sifatini oshirish bo'yicha ilmiy-uslubiy tavsiyalar berilgan. [129].

Pedagog olim N. A. Muslimov bo'lajak kasb ta'limi o'qituvchisida kasbiy-pedagogik sifatlarni shakllantirishning ilmiy-metodik asoslarini tadqiq etib, mutaxassislarning yangi avlodini shakllantirish, ma'naviy-ahloqiy jihatdan yetuk, mustaqil dunyoqarashga ega, ijodiy fikrlovchi, umuminsoniy va milliy qadriyatlarga sadoqatli barkamol shaxsni tarbiyalab, voyaga yetkazish masalalariga alohida e'tibor qaratgan. [120].

Aynan mana shunday yuksak sifatlarga ega bo'lish nafaqat bo'lajak kasb ta'limi, balki bo'lajak o'qituvchilar kelgusidagi axborot kompetentligi faolligining muvaffaqiyatini ta'minlaydi, deb ayta olamiz.

Ilmiy tadqiqotlarning tahliliga ko'ra, M. Abdullayeva, L. Qurbonovalarning ishlarida ijod, ilmiy ijod, ilmiy-ijodiy tafakkur, ijod jarayonida ratsionallik va irratsionallik muammosi bo'yicha izlanishlar olib borilgan. Tadqiqotchi A. V. Morozovning fikricha, pedagogik qobiliyatlar pedagogik ijodkorlik qobiliyatining rivojlanishiga ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Ilmiy izlanishlar natijasi sifatida ijod tushunchasiga turli xil ta'riflari keltirilgan. A. Z. Rahimov ijodning mohiyatini aks ettiruvchi 125 ta eng asosiy mazmunli birikmalarni ajratib ko'rsatadi. Keyinchalik ular to'rtta mavzuviy guruhlariga ajratildi. I. A. Sharshov esa tasniflashni 10 ta guruhgacha to'ldirdi: 1) ijod mezoni sifatida yangilikka tayanish; 2) ongsiz ijod; 3) ijodkor shaxsning o'ziga xos sifatlarini qarab chiqish; 4) ijod jarayon sifatida; 5) natijaga yo'nalganlik; ijodning "oxirgi mahsuloti", 6) ijod faoliyat sifatida, 7) ijod darajalarini aniqlash; 8) ijodiy faoliyat yo'nalishlariga bog'liq bo'lgan nazariyalar; 9) ijod aqliy qobiliyatlar nuqtai nazaridan; 10) ijod integral hodisa sifatida.

Tadqiqotlarda shaxsning yetakchi tavsifnomasi sifatida uning yo'naltirilganligi ko'rsatiladi. Shaxsning rivojlanishi ichki va tashqi omillar bilan belgilanadi, ichki omillarga – fiziologik va biokimyoviy, tashqi omilga-ijtimoiy muhit kiradi. Bu omillar birgalikda amal qiladi, shaxs rivojlanishi sur'ati va darajasi ularning o'zaro kesishuvi bilan belgilanadi.

Tadqiqot ishida shaxsning qobiliyatlar deb ataluvchi tashkil etuvchisini rivojlantirishning o'ziga xos tomonlari o'rganilgan. Qobiliyat-individual ifodalanganlik o'lchoviga ega bo'lgan samaradorligini aniqlovchi, psixologik funksional tizimning tizimiy xossasidir. Ijod-bu sifat jihatidan yangiligi, takrorlanmasligi, originalligi va ijtimoiy-tarixiy noyobligi ajralib turadi. Ba'zi adabiyotlarda kreativlik va ijodkorlikka bitta tushuncha sifatida qaraladi. Ushbu tadqiqot ishida “ijodkorlik” va “kreativlik” tushunchalarini farqlash uchun ikkita tavsifnomadan foydalaniladi: jarayonli-natijaviy (ijodkorlikni belgilash uchun) va sub`ektiv-shartli (kreativlikni belgilash uchun).

Tadqiqot natijalarining ko'rsatishicha, innovatsion faollik tushunchasi mustaqil mavjud bo'lish huquqiga ega, chunki ijodiy qobiliyatlari asosan faoliyat shaklida, ya'ni ijodkorlik faoliyati shaklidagi inson faolligiga taalluqli. O'z navbatida shaxs intellektual faolligi darajalari quyidagilarga ajratiladi: rag`batlantiruvchi-natijaviylikka intilish; evristik-qiyosiy tahlil qilish; kreativ-muammoli masalalarda qonuniyatlarni izlash, muammolarni his qilish, ularni qo'yish.

Ilmiy tadqiqot ishida aniqlanishicha, ijodning boshqa ko'plab (ilmiy, badiiy, texnikurlari bilan umumiylikka ega bo'lgan pedagogik ijod ma'lum o'ziga xosliklarga ega. Pedagogik ijod jarayoni doimiy o'z-o'zini tahlil va o'z-o'zini baholashni talab qiladi. Pedagogik ijodning eng muhim o'ziga xosligi pedagogik jamoaning ijod jarayoni bilan bog'liqligi sanaladi. Pedagogik jamoa, ijodiy jamoa bo'lib, o'z muhitida doimiy yuzaga keladigan pedagogik masalalar bilan shug'ullanadi. Nizoli vaziyatlar va ziddiyatlarni bartaraf etish o'z-o'zini tanqid qilishni rivojlantiradi, pedagogik vazifalarni hal qilishning yangi yo'llari va

vositalarini izlashga majbur etadi, bu esa ijodiy jarayon sanaladi. Pedagogik jamoa bilan hamkorlikda ijod qilish katta rag`batlantiruvchi potensialga ega, bu pedagogni o`z ijodiy faoliyati doirasini kengaytirish va shaxsiy sifatlarini faol namoyon qilishga undaydi.

Ijod butun pedagogik faoliyatni shunchaki qamrab olmasdan, balki o`qituvchining kasbiy mezonlaridan biri sanaladi. Pedagogik kasbning o`ziga xosliklari sirasiga uning natijalarini uzoq kutish kerakligi va ular haqida faqat qisman yakunlar bo`yicha mulohaza yuritish mumkin ekanligi kiradi. Bu o`ziga xos o`qituvchi shaxsiga talablar qo`yadi:u pedagogik ta`sir oqibatlarini bashorat qila bilishi, muntazam ravishda maqsadli "ijod qilish"qobiliyatiga ega bo`lish lozim.Pedagogik ijod o`quv-tarbiya jarayoni bilan uyg`unligi bois u doimo ijobiy natijalar berishi kerak.

Hozirgi jamiyatda mamlakatning rivojlanish darajasini nafaqat texnik holati, balki oliy ta'lim muassasalarida tayyorlanayotgan mutaxassislar kasbiy komponentligi ham belgilab beradi. Pedagogika fanida integratsiya va differensiyaning o`zaro ta'siri isbotlangan bo`lib, u kasb-hunar ta'limini tartibga solish, ierarxik model qurish uchun zarur shart-sharoitlarni yaratish imkoniyatini beradi.

REFERENCES

1. Dilshodbek o`g`li, R. S., & Boxodirjon o`g`li, V. A. (2022). XORIJ PSIXOLOGLARINING ISHLARIDA SHAXSNING TADQIQ ETILISHI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 39-47.
2. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). LINGVISTIK TADQIQOTLARDA KORPUS O`RGANISH OBYEKTI SIFATIDA. *IJTIMOIIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 176-182.
3. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). Basic theoretical principles of corpus linguistics. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(2), 1-3.

4. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). PRAGMALINGVISTIKA VA UNING TAHLILIY SHAKLLANISH TARIXI. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 99-105.
5. Ботирова, Н. (2020). Обучающие возможности тестовых технологий. *Профессиональное образование и общество*, (3), 68-71.
6. Ботирова, Н. Д. (2019). Развитию продуктивного мышления младших школьников. *Гуманитарный трактат*, (61), 4-6.
7. Ботирова, Н. Д. Развитию продуктивного мышления младших школьников development of productive thinking of younger schoolboys. *Журнал выпускается ежемесячно, публикует статьи по гуманитарным наукам. Подробнее на, 4.*
8. Ботирова, Н. Д., & Алимджонова, М. Ю. (2022). БЎЛАЖАК БОШЛАНҒИЧ СИНФ ЎҚИТУВЧИЛАРИНИ ЭВРИСТИК ФАОЛИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ ТАШКИЛИЙ ОМИЛЛАРИ. *Scientific progress*, 3(4), 519-524.
9. Botirova Nasiba Djurabayevna INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS . *Eastern European Scientific Journal Germany*. 128 – 132 p. <http://www.auris-verlag.de>
10. Alimjanova, M. (2020). PEDAGOGICAL SYSTEM OF FORMATION OF RESPONSIBILITY IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF NATIONAL VALUES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 914-917.
11. Alimjonova, M. Y. (2021). The role of the national values in the history of pedagogical education. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(3), 1040-1044.
12. Alimjanova, M. (2021). ABOUT GENDER STEREOTYPES. *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL)*, 2(06), 72-76.
13. Janabergenova, A. J. (2018). Organization and Forms of Students' Independent Work on Higher Mathematics at Pedagogical University. *Eastern European Scientific Journal*, (2).
14. Janabergenova, A. J. (2021). Setting Goals on Smart Techniques and Affecting

Student Motivation. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 9333-9336.

15. Askarova, D. (2022). FORMATION OF CREATIVITY AND BOOKREADERS QUALITIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 1039-1044.

16. Askarova, D. I. (2022). The Role Of Folk Pedagogy In The Development Of Creativity Of Students Of Higher Educational Institutions. *Oriental Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(02), 89-96.

17. Dilafruz, A. (2022). Maktabgacha Yoshdagi Bolalarda Va Oilada Gender Xususiyatlarni Shakllantirish Omillari. *Innovation In The Modern Education System*, 2(18), 183-189.

18. Askarova, D. I. (2022). USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN DEVELOPING CREATIVITY OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS. *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL)*, 3(10), 92-97.

19. Askarova, D. I., & Jabborova, M. K. (2022). The Introduction Of Gender Issues In Preschool Education On The Example Of Folk Pedagogy. *Oriental Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(05), 81-87.

20. Nurmamatovna, K. S. (2021). The object of pragmatics—the basic of progmatical approach. *Thematics Journal Of Social Sciences*, 7(5).

21. Hakimov, M. X., & Shokirova, H. N. (2021). Personal dexterity options. *Academicia: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(5), 789-797.

22. Erkinovna, N. S. (2022). Educational Methods in Teaching the Russian Language. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(11), 260-263.

23. Erkinovna, N. S. (2022). THE IMPORTANCE OF LISTENING SKILLS IN LEARNING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 138-145.

24. Erkinovna, N. S. (2022). MECHANISMS OF EFFECTIVE TEACHING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES USING INNOVATIVE METHODS. *Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 11, 132-135.
25. E. Najmiddinov, A. Rasujonov, & J. Rahimov (2022). FARG'ONA VODIYSI SUV HAVZALARIDAGI BALIQLAR GELMINTLARI. *Science and innovation*, 1 (D8), 145-151. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7335759
26. Najmiddinov, Eldor , Rasuljonov, Adhamjon, & Rahimov, Javohir (2022). FISH HELMINTHS IN FISH RESERVOIRS OF FERGANA VALLEY. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2 (10), 1049-1054.
27. E. Najmiddinov (2022). ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА “ИХТИОЛОГИЯ ВА ГИДРОБИОЛОГИЯ” СОҶАЛАРИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ. *Science and innovation*, 1 (D8), 152-160. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7335800
28. E. Najmiddinov (2022). TABIATNING MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM YOSHIDAGI BOLALARNI BARKAMOL AVLOD BO'LIB SHAKLLANISHIDAGI AHAMIYATI. *Science and innovation*, 1 (B8), 149-154. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7336353
29. Юлдашев, Э., & Нажмиддинов, Э. (2013). БРАКОНИДЫ (Hymenoptera, Braconidae) РОДА ROGAS NEES ФАУНЫ СРЕДНЕЙ АЗИИ. In *Биоразнообразие и рациональное использование природных ресурсов* (pp. 134-136).
30. Нажмиддинов, Э. Х., Кучбоев, А. Э., Мухаммадиев, М. А., & Соатов, Б. Б. (2021). Эколого-морфологические характеристики нематод рода *Rhabdochona*-паразитов обыкновенной маринки. *Теория и практика борьбы с паразитарными болезнями*, (22), 387-393.
31. Kuchboev, A. E., Najmidinov, E. K., Mukhamediev, M. A., Karimova, R. R., & Yildiz, K. (2021). Morphological and ecological features of some nematodes of the genus *Rhabdochona* in marinka obtained from Fergana Valley,

Uzbekistan. *Journal of Parasitic Diseases*, 45(4), 1084-1089.

32. Uljaevna, U. F., & Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Development and education of preschool children. *Academicia: an international multidisciplinary research journal*, 11(2), 326-329.
33. Shavkatovna, S. R. N. (2021). METHODOICAL SUPPORT OF DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *Conferencea*, 74-76.
34. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *Conferencea*, 97-102.
35. Oljayevna, O., & Shavkatovna, S. (2020). The Development of Logical Thinking of Primary School Students in Mathematics. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 8(2), 235-239.
36. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Methodological Support for The Development of Primary School Students' Creative Activities. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 2, 121-123.
37. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Improvement of methodological pedagogical skills of developing creative activity of primary school students. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(10), 289-292.

38. Ra'noxon, S. (2022). BOSHLANG'ICH MAKTAB O'QUVCHILARIDA MATEMATIKAGA MUNOSABAT. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 203-207.
39. Шарофутдинова, Р., & Абдуллаева, С. (2022). ФИКРЛАШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА МЕНТАЛ АРИФМЕТИКА. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 235-239.
40. Asqarov Anvarjon Rahimjon o'g'li. (2022). МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDAGI BOLALARNING AQLIY TARAQQIYOTINING RIVOJLANISHIDA O'YIN RIVOJLANTIRUVCHI FAOLIYAT SIFATIDA. *Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 5, 207–209.
41. Askarov, A. (2022). CREATIVE THINKING IN PRESCHOOL SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 87-91.
42. To'lqinovna, Y. D. (2022). МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA MATEMATIK TASAVVURLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH METODLARI. *BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 25-31.
43. Yuldasheva Dilshoda To'lqinovna (2022). МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDAGI

BOLALARDA BADIY TASVIRLAR ORQALI IZCHIL NUTQNI RIVOJLANTIRISH. *Science and innovation*, 1 (1), 741-750. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.653521

44. Yuldasheva, D. (2021). AGE AND THE SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(04), 124-130.
45. Tulkinovna, Y. D. (2021). On the Principle of Simple to Complex in the Development of Speech in Young Children. *International Journal of Culture and Modernity*, 10, 32-35.
46. Ummatqulov, T. (2022). INSON SOG'LOM BO'LISHIDA VALEOLOGIYA FANINING AHAMIYATI. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture*, 2(12), 80-88.
47. SultonaliMannopov, A., AbdusalomSoliev, U., & TokhirShokirov, R. (2021). Development of Uzbek National Singing Art during Independence. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 6845-6853.
48. Rahmonov, U., Ergashev, A., Nazhmetdinova, M., & Usmonova, S. (2021, November). IN THE FORMATION OF THE SOCIO-SPIRITUAL THINKING OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE MUSICAL ART OF THE GREAT SCHOLARS OF THE EASTERN RENAISSANCE POSITION HELD. In *Archive of Conferences* (pp. 36-39).

49. Karimovich, U. R., Mamasodikovna, N. M., & Abdullaevich, E. A. (2021). The Role and Importance of Music Clubs in The Leisure of Young People. *Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices*, 2(2), 47-49.
50. Rahmonov, U., Ergashev, A., Atabaeva, S., & Dilfuzakhon, S. Y. (2021, December). THE ROLE OF THE SPIRITUAL ENVIRONMENT IN THE PENETRATION OF POP MUSIC IN UZBEKISTAN. In *Archive of Conferences* (pp. 51-53).
51. Rahmonov, U., Ergashev, A., Atabaeva, S., & Dilfuzakhon, S. Y. (2021, December). THE ROLE OF THE SPIRITUAL ENVIRONMENT IN THE PENETRATION OF POP MUSIC IN UZBEKISTAN. In *Archive of Conferences* (pp. 51-53).
52. Ulugbek, R. (2021, January). AN ANALYSIS OF WORDS WHOSE EMOTIONAL MEANING CHANGES IN MODERN ENGLISH LINGUISTICS. In *Euro-Asia Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 131-136).
52. Qizi, G. S., & Umarova, N. R. (2021). The use of anthroponyms and pseudonyms in alisher Navoi's gazelles. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(9), 349-353.
53. Tillaboyeva, G., & Umarova, N. R. (2021). ALISHER NAVOIY ASARLARIDA BADIY TAXALLUSLARNING QO‘LLANILISHI. *Студенческий вестник*, (13-5), 70-72.
54. Tillaboyeva, G. S. Q. (2022). ALISHER NAVOIY SHE’RIYATIDA “SHAXS” TUSHUNCHASI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(2), 182-196.
55. Tillaboyeva, G. S. Q. (2022). TILSHUNOSLIKDA LIBOS NOMLARI. *Scientific progress*, 3(4), 506-514.
56. Mohinur, D., & Rahimjon, U. (2022). A Study Of Memory Processes And Their Development In Preschool. *Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 5, 62-65.

57. Rahim, U. (2021, May). SOCIAL FACTORS OF THE INTERDEPENDENCE OF MENTAL AND PHYSICAL ACTIVITY. In *Archive of Conferences* (Vol. 25, No. 1, pp. 6-7).
58. Usmonov, R. (2022). O'SMIRLAR XULQIDA NAMOYISHKORLIK G'AYRATLILIK XUSUSIYATLARI TADQIQ ETISH METODOLOGIYASI. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 127-135.
59. Usmonov, R. (2022). O'SMIRLIK DAVRI SHAXSIGA XOS ILMIY-NAZARIY YONDOSHUVLAR. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 120-126.
60. Raxmonovich, U. R. (2022). O'SMIRLIK DAVRIDA NAMOYISHKORLIK, G'AYRATLILIK TAJOVUZKORLIK XUSUSIYATLARINING NAMOYON BO'LISHI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 87-97.
61. Raxmonovich, U. R. (2022). O'SMIRLIK DAVRIDA NAMOYISHKORLIK, G'AYRATLILIK TAJOVUZKORLIK XUSUSIYATLARINING NAMOYON BO'LISHI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 87-97.
62. Rakhmonovich, U. R. (2022). CHARACTERISTICS OF DEMONSTRATIVENESS, ENTHUSIASM AND AGGRESSIVENESS IN ADOLESCENCE. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(12), 820-824.
63. Qurbonova, S. (2022). KICHIK MAKTAB YOSHIDAGI BOLALARDA AQLIY INTELLEKTNING RIVOJLANISHI. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture*, 2(12), 73-79.

64. Қурбонова, С. (2022). ПСИХОЛОГИЯНИ ЎҚИТИШГА ЗАМОНАВИЙ ПЕДАГОГИК ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРНИ ТАТБИҚ ЭТИШ. *MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH*, 2(17), 191-194.
65. Qurbonova, S. (2022, June). ON THE ANALYSIS OF LEXICAL UNITS IN PSYCHOLINGUISTICS. In *International Conference on Research Identity, Value and Ethics* (pp. 512-513).
66. Miralimjanovna, Q. S. (2022). О ‘SMIRLIK DAVRIDA TURLI XIL QATLAMGA EGA BOLGANLARNING PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 30, 39-44.
67. Miralimjanovna, Q. S. (2022). CHET EL OLIMLARI TOMONIDAN GURUHDAGI O ‘SMIRLAR VA AUTSAYDERLAR MUAMOSINI O ‘RGANILISHNING OZIGA XOSLIGI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 30, 33-38.
68. Noxida, D., & Saida, Q. (2022). TALABA QIZLARNI OILAVIY HAYOTGA TAYYORLASHNING ETNOPSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(11), 309-314.
69. Dilshodbek O'g'li, R. S. (2022). The Role Of Physical Culture In Providing The Psychological Health Of The Athlete. *Innovative Developments And Research In Education, Canada*.
70. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S. (2022). TALABALARDA TOLERANTLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH–IJTIMOIY PSIXOLOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 30, 66-70.

71. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S. (2022). PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE

SPORTSMAN PERSONALITY DURING COMPETITIONS. *IJTIMOIIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 215-221.

72. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S. (2022). Motiv Va Motivatsiya Muammosining Jahon Va Mahalliy Psixologlar Tomonidan Tadqiq Etilganligi. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(11), 256-259.
73. Qurbonova, S. (2022). KICHIK MAKTAB YOSHIDAGI BOLALARDA AQLIY INTELLEKTNING RIVOJLANISHI. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture*, 2(12), 73-79.
74. Курбонова, С. (2022). ПСИХОЛОГИЯНИ ЎҚИТИШГА ЗАМОНАВИЙ ПЕДАГОГИК ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРНИ ТАТБИҚ ЭТИШ. *MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH*, 2(17), 191-194.
75. Qurbonova, S. (2022, June). ON THE ANALYSIS OF LEXICAL UNITS IN PSYCHOLINGUISTICS. In *International Conference on Research Identity, Value and Ethics* (pp. 512-513).
76. Miralimjanovna, Q. S. (2022). O 'SMIRLIK DAVRIDA TURLI XIL QATLAMGA EGA BOLGANLARNING PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 30, 39-44.
77. Miralimjanovna, Q. S. (2022). CHET EL OLIMLARI TOMONIDAN GURUHDAGI O 'SMIRLAR VA AUTSAYDERLAR MUAMMOSINI O 'RGANILISHNING OZIGA XOSLIGI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 30, 33-38.
78. Noxida, D., & Saida, Q. (2022). TALABA QIZLARNI OILAVIY HAYOTGA TAYYORLASHNING ETNOPSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(11), 309-314.
79. Kakharovna, A. M., Tadjimatovich, Y. M., Rakhmatovich, S. O., & Mirzahamdammovna, Q. B. (2021). Modern Approaches to the Teaching of Fine Arts. *Solid State Technology*, 64(2), 4250-4254.

80. Nazokat, A., Ibrokhim, Y., & Makhpuzakhon, A. (2021). FACTORS OF DEVELOPMENT OF FINE ARTS.

81. M. Ahmedbekova (2022). ЁШ АВЛОДНИНГ БАДИИЙ-ЭСТЕТИК ИЖОДҚОРЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА ТАСВИРИЙ САЊЪАТНИНГ ЖАМИЯТДАГИ ЎРНИ ВА АҲАМИЯТИ. *Science and innovation*, 1 (B8), 112-119. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7336303

82. Kipchakova, Y. (2021). METHODOLOGICAL AND DIDACTIC ASPECTS OF INFORMATION AND INTELLECTUAL CULTURE IN THE EDUCATION OF A DEVELOPED GENERATION. *Экономика и социум*, (6-1), 156-159.

83. Kipchakova, Y. X., & Kodirova, G. A. (2020). INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN MODERN EDUCATION. *Теория и практика современной науки*, (5), 29-31.

84. KIPCHAKOVA, Y., ABDUXAMIDOVA, M., & RAXMONALIYEVA, M. THE IMPACT OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING STUDENT KNOWLEDGE. *СТУДЕНЧЕСКИЙ ВЕСТНИК Учредители: Общество с ограниченной ответственностью "Интернаука"*, 37-38.

85. Қипчақова, Ё., Махмудова, М., & Умарова, З. (2021). МАКТАБГАЧА ЁШДАГИ БОЛАЛАР МЕҲНАТИНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ХУСУСИЯТИ. *Студенческий вестник*, (22-7), 9-10.

86. Қипчақова, Ё., Соибжонова, Ш., & Абдуқаюмова, С. (2021). МАКТАБГАЧА ТАЪЛИМ ЖАРАЁНИДА СОҒЛОМ ТУРМУШ ТАРЗИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ. *Студенческий вестник*, (22-7), 11-12.

87. Матмусаева, М. А. (2017). Оилада болаларни меҳнатга ўргатиш. *Молодой ученый*, (4-2), 23-24.

88. Матмусаева, М. А. (2019). ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ В РАЗВИТИИ ЧУВСТВА РОДИНЫ В ВОСПИТАНИИ ДОШКОЛЬНИКОВ НА ВОСПИТАТЕЛЬНЫХ И ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ

- ЗАНЯТИЯХ. *Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире*, (3-4), 103-106.
- 89.Матмусаева, М. А. (2016). ТАЛАБАЛАР ПОРТФОЛИОЛАРИНИ ТАЙЁРЛАШ ШАРОИТЛАРИ. In *Сборники конференций НИЦ Социосфера* (No. 9, pp. 129-131). Vedecko vydavatelске centrum Sociosfera-CZ sro.
- 90.Матмусаева, М. А. (2016). ТАЛАБАЛАРНИНГ ЎҚУВ ФАОЛИЯТЛАРИНИ НАЗОРАТ ҚИЛИШНИНГ ИННОВАЦИОН ХАРАКТЕРИ. In *Сборники конференций НИЦ Социосфера* (No. 9, pp. 127-128). Vedecko vydavatelске centrum Sociosfera-CZ sro.
- 91.Махамдалиевна, Y. D., & Matmusaeva, M. (2021). On Lingvofolcloristic Units. *International Journal of Culture and Modernity*, 11, 169-171.
- 92.Матмусаева, М. (2022). МАКТАБГАЧА ТАЪЛИМ МУАССАСАСИ– МАКТАБГАЧА ЁШДАГИ БОЛАЛАР ИЖТИМОЙ ТАРБИЯ МАСКАНИ. *IJODKOR O'QITUVCHI*, 2(20), 130-132.
- 93.Matmusayeva, M. A., & Rustamova, N. A. (2021). DEVELOPING LOGICAL THINKING IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (6), 658-660.
- 94.Azamovna, M. M. PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN.
- 95.Nabijonova, F. (2022). Boshlangich sinflarda didaktik oyinlarning ahamiyati: Nabijonova Feruza. *Qo'qon universitetining ilmiy materiallar bazasi*, 1(000006).
- 96.Dilfuza, S., Nabijonova, F., & Matlubaxon, A. (2022). TA'LIM VA O'QITISH NAZARIYASINING MUHIM JIHLTLARI. *INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM*, 2(19), 366-372.